

Open Science Project 2024 - Harkonnen

Version 0

Description

DMP of the project for the Open Science course of the Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge Master's Degree.

The project aims at addressing the following research questions:

1. Is that possible to create a new index of citations which contains typed citations where a peer review (citing entity) reviews (specific citation function) a publication (cited entity)?

2. What is the necessary transformation of the [Crossref](#) dump necessary to create such an index to be compliant with the OpenCitations Data Model?

3. What are the top publication venues in terms of the number of peer reviews received?

4. How many peer reviews in Crossref are included in [OpenCitations Meta](#)?

How many articles that have been reviewed by a peer review are included in OpenCitations Meta?

Funder

University of Bologna

Grant

Open Science course 2023-24

Researchers

Nicole Liggeri (orcid:0009-0006-9417-2648), Matteo Guenci (orcid:0009-0006-3139-1667), Daniele Spedicati (orcid:0009-0002-8965-3480), Chiara Parravicini (orcid:0009-0006-7501-6789)

Organizations
University of Bologna, Italy

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Open Science Project 2024 - Harkonnen](#)

Description:

DMP of the project for the Open Science course of the Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge Master's Degree.

The project's aims at addressing the following research questions:

1. Is it possible to create a new index of citations which contains typed citations where a peer review (citing entity) reviews (specific citation function) a publication (cited entity)?

2. What is the necessary transformation of the [Crossref](#) dump necessary to create such an index to be compliant with the OpenCitations Data Model?

3. What are the top publication venues in terms of the number of peer reviews received?

4. How many peer reviews in Crossref are included in [OpenCitations Meta](#)?
How many articles that have been reviewed by a peer review are included in OpenCitations Meta?

Researchers:

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[Chiara Parravicini \(orcid:0009-0006-7501-6789\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Bologna, Italy](#)

Contact: [Chiara Parravicini](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [University of Bologna](#)

Grants: [Open Science course 2023-24](#)

Project: [OpenScience 2024](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Description of the dataset

Index of citations which contains typed citations where a peer review (citing entity) reviews (specific citation function) a publication (cited entity) obtained combining data from Crossref and OpenCitations Meta.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We are re-using data coming from [Crossref](#) and [OpenCitations](#).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Since our data is a result of a manipulation coming from already existing data it can be considered derived.

1.1.5 What is its format?

RDF

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

OpenCitations Meta and Crossref

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Legal

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

OpenCitations Peer Review Index (OCPRI)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Immediately

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

FAIR

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Nicole Liggeri (orcid:0009-0006-9417-2648)
- b. Daniele Spedicati (orcid:0009-0002-8965-3480)

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- c. Chiara Parravicini (orcid:0009-0006-7501-6789)

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- d. Matteo Guenci (orcid:0009-0006-3139-1667)

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5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

With a doi.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Description of the software

The purpose of the software is to combine data from Open Citation Meta and Crossref to create an output dataset that answers the following research question: "Is that possible to create a new index of citations which contains typed citations where a peer review (citing entity) reviews (specific citation function) a publication (cited entity)? What is the necessary transformation of the Crossref dump necessary to create such an index to be compliant with the OpenCitations Data Model? What are the top publication venues in terms of the number of peer reviews received? How many peer reviews in Crossref are included in OpenCitations Meta? How many articles that have been reviewed by a peer review are included in OpenCitations Meta?"

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

Code in Python

1.1.5 What is its format?

.py

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

It is a new original product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

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2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

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3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

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Yes

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Open

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Yes

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

It will be accessible through the above mentioned github link.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

immediatly

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

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3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

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3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

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Yes

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

FAIR

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

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3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

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